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CARBOHYDRATE DERIVATIVE BENZO(A)PYRENE IN CIGARETTE SMOKE AND HEALTH RISKS OF PASSIVE SMOKERS

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Abstract. It has been revealed that benzo(a)pyrene is not only a background pollutant of the environment, but it is a highly toxic substance that easily enters the body of active and passive smokers through the respiratory tract. This substance is carcinogenic and causes intoxication, as well as various types of complex diseases. Degradation of benzo(a)pyrene in the environment occurs due to ultraviolet radiation, as well as exposure to photooxidants, primarily nitrogen oxides and ozone.

Keywords: Carbohydrates, benzo(a)pyrene, toxicity, carcinogen, identification, passive smoker, correlation.

Introduction

Atmospheric air contains a large amount of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, which have a pronounced carcinogenic effect, which depends on the sequence of articulation of benzene rings. The carcinogenicity of hydrocarbons from the five rings is related to the nature of the addition of the fifth ring.

Benzo(a)pyrene (chemical formula - C₂₀ H₁₂) is a polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon with a molar mass of 252.31 g/mol. There are two isomers. Tobacco smoke contains 1,2-benzo(a) pyrene (3,4 benzopyrene). Its content in the smoke of one cigarette can reach (depending on the nature of the puff and the structure of the tobacco product) an average of 0.025 micrograms, which is more than 10,000 times higher than the maximum allowable concentration. In its form (in its pure form), it is an acicular crystal or light-yellow plate with a melting point of about 177°C. [[1](#); [13](#); [14](#)]

Another isomer is 4,5-benzo(o)pyrene. In its pure form, it is also light-yellow crystals or plates with a melting point of 179°C.

According to hygienic standards, the maximum allowable average daily amount of benzo(a)pyrene in the air (MPC) is 0.1 µg/100.0 m³, and at workplaces, the average shift is not more than 0.00015 mg/m³. According to the results of monitoring, the content of benzo(a)pyrene in the air of large cities exceeds the indicated values from 5 to 12 times.

Being a derivative of pyrene tetracyclic hydrocarbon devoid of carcinogenic activity, the five-ring molecule of 1,2,5,6-dibenzanthracene is capable of causing malignant tumors. Compared to other polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, benzo(a)pyrene is characterized by the greatest

relative stability in environmental objects and has the most pronounced biological, in particular carcinogenic, activity. Between the concentration of benzo(a)pyrene and the total content of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and their carcinogenic activity, a pronounced linear relationship with a high correlation coefficient (0.90) was determined. The contribution of benzo(a)pyrene to the total carcinogenicity prevails and varies from 40.0 to 90.0% compared to other polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons. [[1](#); [2](#); [6](#); [7](#)]

It must be taken into account that the combination of low concentrations with a long duration of exposure causes a stronger negative effect than the combination of high concentrations with a short duration of exposure. Benzo(a)pyrene cannot exist in the biosphere for a long time. It interacts with other pollutants, forming structures that are more toxic than the original substances.

Of the carcinogenic effects of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, the most detailed is determined by the example of the tumorigenic effects of benzapyrene.

According to the International Agency for Research on Cancer, there is no direct epidemiological evidence that benzo(a)pyrene is carcinogenic to humans. Therefore, this compound is assigned to group 2, which indicates only the potential danger of benzapyrene. There is an opinion according to which benzo(a)pyrene can also be attributed to group 1, which includes unconditional carcinogens.

It is believed that the constant intake of benzo(a)pyrene from the environment (passive smoker) leads to a weakening of the immune system of the body of both smokers and non-smokers, contributes to the development of a number of chronic diseases of the digestive, respiratory and nervous systems. We can initiate the development of stomach ulcers, irritation of the upper respiratory tract, increase the risk of coronary heart disease, chronic diseases of the lungs and respiratory system. [[8](#); [9](#); [12](#); [17](#)]

In addition to the fact that benzo(a)pyrene in combination with other polycyclic hydrocarbons provokes the occurrence of a number of oncological diseases, it also contributes to changes in the composition of the blood and causes irreversible mutations (in the DNA complex) that can pass into the next generations.

The degree of danger does not depend on whether benzo(a)pyrene enters the body: through the skin, with food or by inhalation. Taking into account the ubiquity of benzo(a)pyrene in the human environment, it is usually considered the highest priority, environmentally hazardous factor. [[10](#); [12](#)]

Benzo(a)pyrene is almost never found in the free state. It is always deposited on solid particles contained in the air. It is carried by air masses over long distances and falls together with solid particles on all environmental objects. In the migration and accumulation of benzo(a)pyrene, environmental conditions play an important role (humidity, air temperature, degree of illumination, etc.) [[11](#); [16](#)]

Benzo(a)pyrene, like other polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, practically does not exist in a molecularly dispersed state, and necessarily binds with other air pollutants. Of greatest interest is the surface layer of the atmosphere, which contains the main part of the pollution, among which particles of medium dispersion (1.0 - 10.0 microns) are present for a long time in the breathing zone of both active and passive smokers. Larger particles, larger than 10.0 microns, fall out of the air due to sedimentation and are deposited on objects surrounding a person, primarily furniture and food. [[3](#); [4](#); [15](#)]

Research goals

The question of the influence of a specific distance on the content of the separated components of tobacco smoke at a certain time after each "pass" is not only an identification issue. Considering tobacco smoke as an object of a variety of material formations, we strive, as far as possible, to highlight the problem of direct and indirect danger in the biomedical aspect. The main and side stream of smoke, which is especially important for a passive smoker in a long-smoked room with a lower "freshness index".

Another goal is to determine how dangerous benzo(a)pyrene is for human health as a highly toxic substance and what risk factors it contains.

Materials and Research Methods

We carried out a quantitative analysis of benzo(a)pyrene in tobacco smoke at distances of 2.0 m, 4.0 m and 6.0 meters after 3.0 minutes, 5.0 minutes and 10.0 minutes after the "second pass" of a cigarette smoking machine at a temperature room 18.0°C.

Identification of benzo(a)pyrene in cigarette tobacco smoke was carried out by gas chromatography on a PPF-Millipor-Waters chromatograph (USA). According to the "spot sampling" (2.0; 4.0 and 6.0 m.), the analysis was repeated 6 times for each zone (1.0 m³ of air) with an interval of 10 days in order to clean the room. The results were processed on the basis of the SPSS computer program. [1]

Results

Like all aromatic hydrocarbons, it is practically insoluble in water, but it dissolves well in many organic solvents, oils, fats, and therefore accumulates mainly in the adipose tissue of the body, as well as in the lungs of a smoker and a non-smoker.

It has been suggested that oxides of alkali metals formed during pyrolysis are able to react with organic radicals in the burning zone of cigarettes and inhibit the synthesis of aromatic hydrocarbons, including carcinogens. It has also been shown that hexane-soluble tobacco components play a critical role in the formation of aromatic hydrocarbons contained in tobacco smoke pyrolysates. About 2/3 of the benzo(a)pyrene contained in the pyrolyzate is formed from the hexane soluble components of tobacco leaves.

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons: benzo(a)pyrene, benzo(a)anthracene, benzo(a)chrysene, pyr(a)pyrene, benzo(a)fluoranthene are distinguished by increased stability of the aromatic nucleus and a high tendency to substitution reaction.

According to the coplanarity rule, in the series of conjugated aromatic hydrocarbons, the most coplanar compounds have the highest adsorption capacity.

The danger of exposure to second-hand tobacco smoke is determined not only by toxicity, but also by the volatility of each component. Aromatic hydrocarbons are highly volatile. [5; 16] More than 30 components of this class have now been identified in secondhand tobacco smoke, among which benzo(a)pyrene occupies a special place.

Benz (e) pyrene, identified in side tobacco smoke, is non-carcinogenic according to the Richter system, but serves as the starting material for the formation of many carcinogens. The danger of benzo(a)pyrene is also associated with its ability to spread over considerable distances, to remain indoors in the form of components deposited on the solid and liquid phases (macro particles) of the atmosphere.

The table shows the average values of the content of benzo(a)pyrene in 1.0 m³ of air at a distance of 2.0, 4.0 m and 6.0 meters from a burning cigarette.

According to the data obtained, 3.0 minutes after the second "pass", the level of benzo(a)pyrene at a distance of 2.0 m from the source is 5.2 ± 0.4 ppm. At a distance of 4.0 m does not exceed 5.9 ± 0.3 ppm, and at a distance of 6.0 m. 5.4 ± 0.4 ppm ($P > 0.05$). Thus, 3.0 minutes after the second "pass", the level of benzo(a)pyrene at a distance of 2.0 m, 4.0 m and 6.0 m from the source is almost the same. 5.0 minutes after the second "pass", the level of benzo(a)pyrene at a distance of 2.0 m was 4.2 ± 0.2 ppm. At a distance of 4.0 m, it increased significantly and reached 6.0 ± 0.5 ppm (significant difference $P < 0.001$). At six meters' distance, the content of benzo(a)pyrene reached 7.9 ± 0.5 ppm ($P < 0.001$).

Thus, at the fifth minute after the second "pass", the level of benzo(a)pyrene begins to grow with distance from the source and increases according to each distance. The content of benzo(a)pyrene 10.0 minutes after the second "pass" reached 8.5 ± 0.9 ppm at a distance of 2.0 m from the source. In the specified period of time, its level at a distance of 4.0 m was significantly higher (10.9 ± 0.9 ppm, $P < 0.001$). In the matrix taken at a distance of 6.0 m, an even greater increase was confirmed (13.2 ± 1.1 ppm, $P < 0.001$). Thus, within 10.0 minutes after the second "pass", the level of benzo(a)pyrene increases with distance from the source and is highest at a distance of 6.0 m after 10.0 minutes (13.2 ± 1.1 ppm, $P < 0.001$).

Comparative analysis, carried out according to the time of sampling, revealed the following: After 3.0 min. after the second "pass" at a distance of 2.0 m from the source, the level of benzo(a)pyrene is 5.2 ± 0.4 ppm. At the same distance after 5.0 minutes, it decreased significantly and did not exceed 4.2 ± 0.2 ppm. The difference is significant ($P < 0.001$). However, 10.0 minutes after the second "pass", the content of benzo(a)pyrene increased sharply (8.5 ± 0.9 ppm, $P < 0.001$). At a distance of 4.0 m from the source, the level of benzo(a)pyrene 3.0 and 5.0 minutes after the second "pass" is almost the same (5.9 ± 0.3 ppm and 6.0 ± 0.5 ppm, respectively, $P > 0.05$). However,

in the sample taken after 10.0 minutes, this indicator was significantly higher (10.9 ± 0.9 ppm, $P < 0.001$). Thus, in 3.0 and 5.0 minutes after the second "pass", the level of benzo(a)pyrene at a distance of 4.0 m from the source is practically the same and only increases significantly at 10 minutes. At a distance of 6.0 m, the content of benzo(a)pyrene, depending on time, varied as follows: 5.0 minutes after the second "pass", it exceeded the three-minute data (5.4 ± 0.4 and 7.9 ± 0.5 ppm respectively, $P < 0.001$). After 10 minutes increased even more (13.2 ± 1.1 ppm $P < 0.001$). Thus, at a distance of 6.0 m from the source, the level of benzo(a)pyrene increased significantly during the measurement process and turned out to be the highest 10.0 minutes after the second "pass".

According to our data, the highest content of benzo(a)pyrene in side tobacco smoke was identified 10.0 minutes after the second "pass" at a distance of 6.0 meters from the lit cigarette. It is well known that sidestream smoke, unlike the main stream, is formed at an intermediate moment between puffs (passes) and is released from the end of the cigarette into the surrounding air. The average puff frequency for smokers with 10-15 years of experience is 1.0 per minute, the puff volume is about 35.0 ± 10.0 cm³, and the duration of each "pass" is about 3.0 seconds. No more than 40% of the total amount of components contained in cigarette smoke are directly formed from the product itself. The vast majority are products of the ambient atmosphere, extended by the active smoker in the "pass" process. The inhalability of smoke is related to the pH of its individual components and does not exceed pH 5.4 on average. As the number of "passes" increases, the pH value of the smoke increases geometrically.

Depending on the pH value, the degree of protonation and, naturally, the percentage of minor components change not only in the gaseous, but also in the vapor phases of cigarette smoke. From a physicochemical point of view, tobacco smoke is represented by solid (particulate), gaseous and vapor phases.

According to the data presented in the work, the smallest amount of benzo(a)pyrene in cigarette smoke was identified 5.0 minutes after the second "pass" at a distance of 2.0 meters. In this question, the leading importance of photochemical processes is usually emphasized. The role of the solid and liquid phases (macroparticles) is also considered important as an obligatory substance of the atmosphere, capable of not only fixing tobacco smoke components for a long time, but also taking an active part in oxidative reactions.

It should also be taken into account that polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, including benzo(a)pyrene, are characterized by increased stability of the aromatic series and a high tendency to substitution reactions.

It has been established that about 2/3 of the smoke of a cigarette smoked to the end enters the atmosphere that a "passive smoker" breathes. For every 100 cigarettes smoked, the content of benz(a)pyrene in 1.0 m³ of tobacco smoke ranges from 1.0 to 20.0 µg. It is believed that the ratio of the concentration of benzo(a)pyrene in the mainstream and sidestreams of tobacco smoke is usually 2.5-3.5, respectively. For example, for benzo(a)pyrene, the toxicity index in tobacco smoke corresponds to 17.400 with a toxicity fraction of no more than 4.5. The solid phase of tobacco smoke (tar, tobacco tar), being in an aerosol state, can linger in the alveoli of the lungs, causing cancers of the oral cavity and nose, respiratory tract, lungs, gastrointestinal tract, genitourinary system, etc.

According to the existing requirements for products of the tobacco industry, the content of tar in the smoke should not exceed 21.1 mg per 1 cigar. For this purpose, all kinds of absorbers are added to the products, however, they also take part in pyrolytic reactions.

Most of the genotoxic and carcinogenic substances are in the solid-dispersed phase of stale tobacco smoke. Benzo(a) pyrene is a subfraction of the solid phase (tar) of a highly concentrated concentrate (0.09% of the total weight of the resin) and, as a percentage of the total toxicity of tobacco smoke, is about 4.6%. As shown in 1939 According to the Brazilian scientist A. Raffo, benzo(a)pyrene has multidirectional attack targets and belongs to substances of the 1st hazard class.

The connection between organic compounds present in cigarette smoke tar and pyrolytic reactions is now clearly emphasized. More than 75 organic compounds, including 34 hydrocarbons, have been identified in the composition of resins. As the amount of nitrates in tobacco increases, the yield of nitroparaffins increases, and confirms the position that, during pyrolysis, nitrogen oxides react with organic radicals in the combustion zone and inhibit the synthesis of aromatic hydrocarbons, including benzo(a)pyrene. At the same time, double-bonded substances contained in tobacco leaves (for example, unsaturated fatty acids, primarily linolenic acid and its methyl esters) during combustion give a relatively high yield of neutral products, including aromatic hydrocarbons. The greatest amount of benzo(a)pyrene is released during the pyrolysis of B-styrene.

It was found that aliphatic unsaturated compounds of tobacco leaves during pyrolysis form toxic pyrolysates in tobacco smoke, with a relatively high yield of neutral substances, in which there are aromatic components with alkyl groups in the side chains. An important precursor of benz(a)pyrene is stearin. An equally effective precursor is the hexane-soluble fraction of tobacco, while stearic acid occupies the smallest place. It is believed that more than 2/3 of the benzo(a)pyrene in tobacco smoke is formed as a result of the pyrolysis of hexane-soluble tobacco components.

Conclusions

Thus, benzo(a)pyrene is dangerous not only as a background environmental pollution, but also as a highly toxic substance that easily penetrates into the body of both a heavy smoker and a non-smoker, into whose body it enters by inhalation.

In addition to accumulation in all objects of the environment, it is partially transformed. In the air, the degradation of benzo(a)pyrene occurs due to exposure to ultraviolet radiation, as well as various photooxidants, primarily ozone and nitrogen oxides. Formaldehyde, acrolein, and organic peroxides actively participate in the degradation of benzo(a)pyrene.

Issues of air pollution by tobacco smoke are related not only to the concentration and duration of existence of each component, but also to their volatility (spread). It is necessary to take into account the nature of the turbulence of the air environment, as well as the ability of segmentation of each component.

Also, the level of benzo(a)pyrene in cigarette smoke to which a passive smoker is exposed is strongly related to distance and time. This dependence naturally includes a number of other "perturbing factors", but they are not considered in the structure of the proposed work.

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